

Classic Kaposi's Sarcoma in an exclusively cutaneous exhibition

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ABSTRACT Kaposi's sarcoma is rare in HIV negative patients and is associated with HHV-8 (human herpes virus) infection. Lesions are usually solitary and can be treated surgically. Exceptional cases of Kaposi's have started to gather, and an example of such is the one we have reported. Here we establish a case report on Kaposi's sarcoma in a young immune-competent male patient who presented with exclusively cutaneous lesions on the axilla and right side of the chest without involving the lungs or any other viscera. The clinical examination, radiological investigations, biopsy and antibody tests were done to evaluate the presumptive diagnosis and the relevant literature reviewed.

KEYWORDS Kaposi's sarcoma, exclusive skin involvement, immuno-competent, young

Introduction

Kaposi's sarcoma is a low-grade mesenchymal tumour which mainly affects the skin but later extends to viscera via blood and lymphatic vessels [1]. An infection causes it with either the Human Herpesvirus-8 (HHV-8), Human Papillomavirus 16, Human Papilloma Virus 18 or the Human Cytomegalovirus [2,3]. It occurs in four types, namely, classic, endemic, immunosuppression therapy-related, an epidemic. Classic Kaposi's tends to affect older men, is usually slow growing, and affects the legs [4] while endemic Kaposi's sarcoma is found to be a more aggressive type usually presenting in young adult males in Africa [4] Immunosuppression therapy-related type generally occurs in people following organ transplantation and mostly affects the skin.

Characteristically, Kaposi has been associated with AIDS for centuries, but now and then, new cases of non-HIV affected patients sprout up, leading to further studies over the matter. Bisexual and homosexual men are usually found to be affected with Kaposi more than those with other sexual orientations, but, this number is now decreasing [5] as a variety of cases are now becoming a part of the literature.

Figure 1:

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Figure 2:

Case Report

A 29-year-old male, the resident of Karachi, Pakistan, an ex-smoker (since 1 year) and labourer by profession with no history of known co-morbidities, was presented to the Dermatology department of Dr Ruth K.M.Pfau Civil Hospital in December 2018 with the complain of multiple solid elevated lesions on the right side of his chest and axilla for the last 5 to 6 months.

According to the patient, he was in his usual state of health when six months back, he first noticed these lesions. The lesions were dome-shaped, skin-coloured, and painless with no overlying scales, appearing on the right side of the chest accompanied by itching. No other lesions were present anywhere on the body at that time. For the past three months, he noticed that the lesions increased in number and covered whole right side of chest, axilla and scapular region. The colour of these lesions changed from skin-colour to pink and brown. These new lesions were associated with pain, itch, burning sensation with no discharge of any sort. One month ago, he observed two small painless swellings on his left axilla, which had no association with itch, pain, burning sensation or discharge. He undertook homoeopathic treatment, which reduced the burning sensation and itchiness but had no effect on the size of skin lesions. The patient also reported unintentional weight loss of 3kgs in the last four months. His father had diabetes. His past drug, blood transfusion history and systemic review were also unremarkable. He is married and denies any sexual contact outside wedlock.

On general physical examination, the patient appeared to be of average height and built and well-oriented with time and place. His axillary lymph nodes were palpable bilaterally, firm in consistency and up to 3 cm in size. They were slightly erythematous, non-tender, with normal temperature, mobile and not attached to underlying structures. On cutaneous examination, multiple nodular lesions were present on the right side of the chest, axilla and scapular region [Fig.1]. Lesions were pink to

Figure 3:

brown in colour and varied in size from 1cm to 8cm, non-tender, not warm and firm in consistency. Rest of the general examination was unremarkable. On systemic examination, the abdomen was soft and tender. Splenomegaly was noted around three fingerbreadths below the costal margin. There were no other significant findings.

Baseline tests and several investigations were ordered to investigate the case which included the complete blood count (CBC), erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR), urinalysis, Urea, creatinine and electrolytes (UCE) and viral profile. All of them were found to be unremarkable. Liver function tests (LFTs) were also done with resultant SGPT (ALT) at 50 U/L, SGOT (AST) at 45 U/L and Gamma-Glutamyl Transpeptidase (GGT) at 48 U/L. This showed that AST and GGT were above the upper limit of the normal range. Total protein and protein Albumin/Globulin (A/G) ratio were also elevated.

Abdominal ultrasound showed splenomegaly measuring up to 14 cm with homogenous parenchymal echo pattern. No focal mass was seen, and the splenic vein was not dilated. A chest

Figure 4:

Figure 5:

Figure 6:

X-ray was also ordered, which showed numerous soft tissue nodules on the right lateral chest wall. HIV ELISA and Hepatitis B and C viral markers came out to be negative. Chest and Abdominal CT scan were also ordered. Irregular prominent subcutaneous thickening and multiple peripherally enhancing soft tissue nodules were noted in the right anterolateral chest wall with co-existing chest wall oedema. Multiple enlarged confluent bilateral axillary lymph nodes measuring 2.5 x 4.4 cm were seen. Spleen and multiple mesenteric lymph nodes were enlarged, measuring about 14 cm and 1.3 x 1.0 cm, respectively. No other anomaly was noticed.

Skin biopsy was obtained in which Acid-fast Bacilli (AFB) and fungal cultures were negative. Epidermis appeared to be intact. Underlying dermis revealed non-encapsulated, well circumscribed, vasoformative neoplastic lesions exhibiting proliferating spindle cells forming slit-like vascular spaces filled with red blood cells and PAS-D positive hyaline globules. Frequent mitoses were also observed — [Fig.2]. IHC markers showed negative for actin, desmin, caldesmon, S-100 but diffuse positive for CD31 and CD34. The morphological and IHC markers pointed towards Kaposi Sarcoma.

Biopsy of axillary lymph node showed partial effacement of nodal architecture and was replaced by ill-circumscribed, vasoformative, neoplastic lesion composed of sheets of atypical spindle cells with moderate eosinophilic cytoplasm. Florid extravasations of RBCs, atypical mitoses and PAS-D positive hyaline globules were also observed [Fig.3]. Findings were about those of Kaposi's Sarcoma.

This provisional diagnosis led to further investigations. HIV antibody test, Treponemal test for Syphilis, CD3+/CD4, CD3+/CD8+, T4: T8 ratio, serum IgG, IgM, IgA and CMV were all normal. The final diagnosis was settled to be 'Classic (Sporadic) Kaposi Sarcoma'.

Paclitaxel 120mg, Decadron 8mg and Ondansetron 2mg were given intravenously every week and the patient has improved since then with a marked reduction in size and number of the lesions and no new lesions were erupted. The patient is non-compliant, but still visits Dermatology OPD of Civil Hospital Karachi sometimes. No recurrence has been noted. Unfortunately, HHV-8 testing is not available in Pakistan. Hence, the corresponding status could not be determined.

Discussion

The classic type of Kaposi presents as red-purple papules or nodules or a combination of both on hands and feet [6]. The cellularity of all the types of Kaposi is of spindle and vascular type with slit partitions assorting within the spindles [7].

A biopsy is used as a prime source of investigation, and all the types are treated with either chemotherapy, radiotherapy or a combination of both [8,9]. Radiotherapy has shown to work spectacularly because of the extreme radio-sensitive nature of the lesions [10]. However, in one report of New York, 1991, it has been documented that in about 20% cases lesions still did not regress after an extensive therapy through the presumed regression rate was 68% [11]. In our setup, patients with Kaposi's are usually from a rural background with meagre knowledge on sexually transmitted diseases, and many still do not approach hospitals because of confidentiality of these diseases due to religious reasons. Hence, there is no collection of data on the topic of Kaposi, but the residents and senior doctors are bows exploring the ghastly disease in detail.

In one of the reports published in Journal of European Academy of Dermatology and Venereology (Potouridou I, 1998), multiple non-tender, reddish-violaceous papules, infiltrated plaques, nodules and tumours measuring from 0.5 to 4 cm were found in a heterosexual 40-year-old man. Lesions were present on the feet, including the toes and soles, the calves, thighs, the dorsa of the hands, fingers, palms, the ears and the nose with lymphedema on both legs extending to the thighs [12]. In a different report (Jan A, 2008), a non-HIV infected 45 years old female presented with multiple painful and livid reddish-brown papules, nodules and plaques on both lower limbs which proceeded on to involve the index finger [13]. A multiple reports published in the Journal of Dermatology Case Reports (Altunay, 2012) published a variety of cases seen in Turkey with variable cutaneous presentations of Kaposi, one of them, a 75-year-old male found to be affected with HHV-8 on laboratory testing, had a purplish 1.5x2 cm nodule on the right ankle, a 27 year non-HIV affected heterosexual male who presented with inguinal swelling at first but later on had developed reddish-purple lesions on the helix of the right ear, retro-auricular region, the mental region and the tip of the nose, multiple mobile lymphadenopathies, while, the third case of a 73-year-old heterosexual man with normal laboratory investigations had reddish purple lesions bilaterally on the dorsum of the feet and toes [14]. No visceral involvement was found in either of the cases discussed.

In our patient, who distinctively reported at an age much younger than the one in which a non-HIV Kaposi affected patient reports, we found the lesions specifically appearing in the right chest at first near the axilla and then leading on to involve the whole right side of the chest, axilla and right scapula. The cases reported above barely exhibited a lesion on the chest, mostly involving the extremities, like the patient presented to us. It is interesting to see that this man also has a normal sexual orientation and is immune-competent. His case was concluded to be Kaposi's sarcoma based on morphological features since HHV-8 testing is unfortunately not available in Pakistan.

Competing Interests

None

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None

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